

TESTING OF FIBER COMPOSITES AT

HIGH STRAIN RATES

Isaac M. Daniel
Science Advisor
Theodore Liber
Senior Research Engineer
IIT Research Institute
Chicago, Illinois

An experimental investigation was conducted to determine strain rate effects in fiber composites. Unidirectional composite specimens of boron/epoxy, graphite/epoxy, S-glass/epoxy and Kevlar/epoxy were tested at tensile strain rates of up to 27 m/m/sec. Longitudinal, transverse and in-plane shear properties, including modulus, Poisson's ratio, strength and ultimate strain, were determined by testing 0-, 90- and 10-degree unidirectional coupons. Strains were measured by means of strain gages bonded on the coupons and loads were measured by means of a strain gage load cell. All specimens were loaded in an electrohydraulic loading system. The 0-degree properties which are governed by the fibers do not vary much with strain rate except for the Kevlar/epoxy material which shows an increase in both modulus and strength. The strain rate effects on 90-degree properties were small with a general trend toward higher strength with increasing strain rate. The most noticeable effect was on in-plane shear properties with shear strength values at high strain rates approximately fifteen percent higher than static values.

Introduction

The application of composites to dynamically loaded components and structures, such as jet engine fan blades, exposes them to the hazards of dynamic failure, e.g., foreign object damage in rotating blades. Design of such components requires knowledge and understanding of the dynamic loading, induced wave propagation phenomena and the response of the material to the high strain rates produced. Dynamic material response and wave propagation are interrelated. Strain rates in the range of 250-650 m/m/sec have been measured in boron/epoxy and graphite/epoxy laminates impacted transversely with low density silicon rubber projectiles at velocities up to 250ms^{-1} (820 ft/sec) (1).

Most composite materials of interest to structural applications have been fully characterized under static loading conditions. Related work under dynamic conditions has been limited. Early attempts to measure dynamic properties in composites were limited to determination of elastic and visco-elastic constants by ultrasonic velocity measurements and vibration testing (2,3,4). Attempts to characterize composites at high strain rates were made by Rotem and Lifshitz (5,6) and Armenakas and Sciammarella (7). The former investigated unidirectional and angle-ply E-glass/epoxy laminates under dynamic tensile loading. They achieved strain rates up to 30s^{-1} using an instrumented falling weight apparatus. In their first study of 0-deg. unidirectional E-glass/epoxy they found dynamic strength values of almost three times the static values and a dynamic modulus approximately 50 percent higher than the static (5). They also found that the ultimate strain was not affected much by strain rate. In a later study with angle-ply laminates, Lifshitz found that the initial modulus was unaffected by strain rate and that the dynamic tensile strength was higher than the static, but only by approximately 20 to 30 percent (6).

Armenakas and Sciammarella (7) studied the response of 0-deg. unidirectional glass/epoxy specimens at strain rates up to 500s^{-1} using an explosively driven testing system. The material they tested was a very low fiber-volume composite prepared in the laboratory. They found a linear variation of the modulus with the logarithm of the strain rate. The ultimate strain, however, decreased with increasing strain rate. The latter is in contradiction with the results of Rotem and Lifshitz (5).

Compressive properties of composites (steel-wire reinforced epoxy) were studied by Sierakowski et al. at strain rates up to 1000/sec using a split Hopkinson bar (8). The failure modes at the high strain rates were significantly different from those at lower rates. The initial modulus remained unaffected by strain rate, but the strength increased by as much as 100 percent at the higher rates. The fact that the failure modes were significantly different at high strain rates is partly due to the multiaxial states of stress induced in the short cylindrical specimens by the Hopkinson bar.

More recently the authors conducted an experimental investigation to determine the strain rate effects in unidirectional composite specimens of boron/epoxy, graphite/epoxy, S-glass/epoxy, and Kevlar 49/epoxy (9). Strain rates up to 27s^{-1} were achieved using an electrohydraulic system. Longitudinal, transverse and in-plane shear properties, including modulus, Poisson's ratio, strength and ultimate strain, were determined by testing 0-, 90-, and 10-degree unidirectional coupons. This paper describes procedures and results of that investigation.

Experimental Procedure

Longitudinal (0-degree) tensile properties were obtained using 6-ply coupons 1.27 cm (0.50 in.) wide with a 5.08 cm (2 in.) gage length and tabbed with fiberglass tabs. Transverse (90-degree) tensile properties were obtained using 8-ply coupons, 1.27 cm (0.50 in.) wide with a 7.62 cm (3 in.) gage length. These specimens were instrumented with a two-gage rosette on each side of the specimen. In-plane shear properties were obtained by using 10-degree off axis coupons, 6-ply thick, 1.27 cm (0.50 in.) wide with a 7.62 cm (3 in.) gage length. They were instrumented with a three-gage rosette on each side of the specimen. Boron/epoxy, graphite/epoxy, S-glass/epoxy and Kevlar 49/epoxy specimens for uniaxial tensile testing at 0-, 90- and 10-degrees to the fibers were prepared and instrumented.

These specimens were tested in uniaxial tension at various strain rates. An MTS electro-hydraulic closed-loop system capable of delivering a wide range of input pulses at velocities up to 5.1 ms^{-1} (12,000 in/min) was used. Special fixtures were designed to transmit the loads into the specimens. One tabbed end of the specimen was clamped between two metal grips and connected through a pin to a clevis link attached to the upper stationary crosshead of the loading frame. At the tabbed bottom end two additional fiberglass tabs extending beyond the original tabs were bonded on. These secondary tabs were connected through a pin to a strain gage load cell link. The load cell was in turn connected through a bottom clevis link to the moving load ram of the machine. This clevis to ram attachment was made through a special bolt whose flat round head was inside the clevis, and whose shank passed with a sliding fit through a central hole in the bottom of the clevis and screwed into the ram. An initial clearance of approximately 6.3 mm (1/4 in.) was provided between the bolt head and clevis bottom. When the ram was activated, the clearance allowed the ram and bolt to accelerate to the desired rate before transmitting load to the specimen and produced a more uniform rate of loading. Figure 1 illustrates the experimental set up with a 10-degree off-axis specimen in the loading frame.

Load measurement was done by means of an aluminum load link instrumented with strain gages and connected in series with the specimen as described above. Strain gages from the test specimens and load cell were recorded on oscilloscopes using potentiometric circuits for strain signal conditioning. The overall experimental set-up is shown in Fig. 2.

In all cases above a few quasi-static tests were conducted to provide a reference at very slow rates for specimens of identical geometry. These quasi-static results were used to supplement previously obtained similar results (10,11).

Results and Discussion

Typical load and strain oscilloscope signals for the [0_G] boron/epoxy, graphite/epoxy, S-glass/epoxy specimens are shown in Figs. 3, 4 and 5. Results from these tests as well as corresponding static tests are tabulated in Table I. Results for boron/epoxy show no significant changes in modulus but some increase in strength at the higher strain rates. The ultimate strain remains relatively constant, with one exception at the $5.3 \text{ } \epsilon/\text{sec}$ strain rate where the limit strain is 8.4×10^{-3} . In the case of graphite/epoxy there is a slight increase in modulus with strain rate but no significant changes in strength or limit strain. In the case of S-glass/epoxy there are no significant changes in strength or limit strain. In the case of S-glass/epoxy there are no significant changes in modulus or strength but some trend towards higher ultimate strain at the higher rates of loading. Kevlar 49/epoxy shows a definite increase in modulus with strain rate and some increase in strength. The ultimate strain at the higher rates of loading

Fig. 1. Unidirectional 10-Degree Off-Axis Specimen Mounted In Machine For Testing At High Strain Rates

Fig. 2. Experimental Setup For Testing Composite Specimens at High Strain Rates In Electrohydraulic Testing Machine

200 $\mu\text{s}/\text{div}$

Fig. 3. Load and Strain Records for $[0_6]$ Boron/Epoxy Specimens Loaded in Tension at Strain Rates of 5.3 ϵ/sec and 10.3 ϵ/sec .

500 $\mu\text{s}/\text{div}$

Fig. 4. Load and Strain Records for $[0_6]$ Graphite/Epoxy Specimens Loaded in Tension at Strain Rates of 1.9 ϵ/sec and 5.0 ϵ/sec .

Fig. 5. Load and Strain Records For $[0_6]$ S-Glass/Epoxy Specimens Loaded in Tension At Strain Rates of 4.5 ϵ/sec and 18.8 ϵ/sec (Sweep: 500 $\mu\text{s}/\text{div}$).

Table I

LONGITUDINAL PROPERTIES OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES AT VARIOUS STRAIN RATES

Material	Average Strain Rate (ϵ/sec)	Maximum Strain Rate (ϵ/sec)	Time to Failure (ms)	Modulus E_{11} (GPa (10^6 psi))	Poisson's Ratio ν_{12}	Strength S_{11T} (MPa (ksi))	Ult. Strain ϵ_{11}^u ($10^{-3}\epsilon$)
Boron/Epoxy	1.4×10^{-4}	1.4×10^{-4}	50×10^3	201 (29.2)	0.17	1375 (199)	7.0
	4.2×10^{-4}	4.2×10^{-4}	17×10^3	192 (27.9)	0.18	1350 (196)	7.2
	1.7	1.8	4	215 (31.1)	0.22	-	-
	1.8	2.0	3.6	212 (30.7)	0.21	1216 (176)	6.8
	1.8	2.7	3.9	204 (29.6)	0.23	1456 (211)	7.2
	5.3	5.3	1.6	201 (29.2)	0.20	1622 (235)	8.4
	10.3	10.3	0.7	198 (28.7)	0.20	1430 (207)	6.9
	Graphite/Epoxy	4.2×10^{-4}	4.2×10^{-4}	12×10^3	196 (28.4)	0.25	980 (142)
4.2×10^{-4}		4.2×10^{-4}	14×10^3	202 (29.2)	0.26	1220 (177)	6.0
1.4		1.9	3.8	208 (30.1)	0.14	1007 (146)	5.3
2.6		3.8	2.0	217 (31.5)	0.17	1159 (168)	6.0
3.1		5.0	1.6	207 (30.0)	0.23	1028 (149)	5.3
S-Glass/Epoxy	1.4×10^{-4}	1.4×10^{-4}	250×10^3	50 (7.2)	0.29	1773 (257)	35.6
	4.2×10^{-4}	4.2×10^{-4}	77×10^3	53 (7.7)	0.28	1545 (224)	32.5
	4.5	4.5	4.6	52 (7.6)	0.22	1290 (187)	30.5
	4.6	4.6	7.2	48 (7.0)	0.25	1552 (225)	37.5
	4.2	4.8	7.3	47 (6.8)	0.26	1332 (193)	35.1
	16.0	16.0	2.3	50 (7.3)	0.28	1780 (258)	38.4
	18.8	18.8	2.0	50 (7.3)	0.26	1787 (259)	38.6
Kevlar 49/Epoxy	1.4×10^{-4}	1.4×10^{-4}	138×10^3	69 (10.0)	0.40	1425 (207)	19.4
	4.2×10^{-4}	4.2×10^{-4}	48×10^3	72 (10.5)	0.33	1533 (222)	20.0
	3.0	9.6	4.1	79 (11.4)	0.40	1204 (175)	18.9
	3.2	11.7	4.0	78 (11.3)	0.43	1323 (192)	18.6
	15.0	15.0	1.1	83 (12.0)	0.38	1546 (224)	18.5
	15.0	15.0	1.2	83 (12.0)	0.33	1622 (235)	19.0

is slightly lower than for static loading. In this series of tests where the properties of the composites are dominated by the fibers trends of properties with increasing strain rate are barely detectable. This is due primarily to the fact that the properties of the fiber materials, with the possible exception of Kevlar, are not very rate dependent, and due to the small number of specimens.

Unidirectional eight-ply 90-degree specimens of the four materials above were tested in tension to failure statically and at various high strain rates. A more sensitive load cell link was designed and used in these tests. Strain rates ranged from quasi-static to 27 ϵ /sec. Typical load and strain records are shown in Figs. 6 through 9. Results from these tests as well as corresponding static tests are tabulated in Table II. In the boron/epoxy the modulus and strength are generally lower than corresponding static values, except for the highest strain rates, 19 and 27 ϵ /sec, where the strength is higher than the static one. The ultimate strain at the high strain rates is, with one exception, much higher than the static values. There is no plausible explanation for these results. In the graphite/epoxy there is some increase in modulus and strength at the higher rates of loading accompanied by an increase in limit strain. In the S-glass/epoxy there seems to be an unlikely reduction in modulus with strain rate, a fact which may not be significant. There is some trend toward higher strength with increasing strain rate. No significant trends in limit strain are apparent. The Kevlar 49/epoxy specimens were too fragile to handle in the electrohydraulic machine and failed at very low loads. The results above do not show any drastic changes of properties with strain rate although these properties are governed by the matrix, which should be more rate dependent.

Unidirectional six-ply specimens of the four materials above were tested in uniaxial tension at 10-degrees to the fiber direction statically and at various high strain rates. These specimens were instrumented with a three-gage rosette on each side. Signals from the load cell and from the longitudinal, transverse and 45-degree gages were recorded on four oscilloscopes. Axial strain rates ranged from quasi-static to 7.7 ϵ /sec. Typical load and strain records are shown in Figs. 10 through 12. Results from these tests as well as corresponding static tests are tabulated in Table III. In the boron/epoxy both the in-plane shear modulus and shear strength show an increase with strain rate. The limit shear strain at the high rates of loading, however, is lower than the corresponding static one. The trends in graphite/epoxy are similar to those in boron/epoxy, with shear modulus and shear strength increasing with strain rate. No significant trends were noticed in the S-glass/epoxy and Kevlar/epoxy materials. Properties obtained at high strain rates were comparable with those obtained statically for the same batch of specimens.

Conclusion

Electrohydraulic systems, such as the one used in this study, are capable of applying medium strain rates up to approximately 50 m/m/sec to coupon specimens with gage lengths of the order of 5 cm (2 in.). In this medium strain rate regime wave propagation effects are neglected and uniform stresses and strains are assumed in the test specimen. For higher strain rates, both the loading system and the specimen configuration must be changed.

In the strain rate regime investigated here strain rate effects were not very pronounced. The 0-degree properties which are governed by the fibers did not vary much with strain rate except for the Kevlar 49/epoxy which showed a definite increase in modulus and strength with strain rate because the fibers in this case have more rate dependent properties. The effects of strain rate on 90-degree properties were also small. In general, a slight

Fig. 6. Load and Strain Records for $[90_8]$ Boron/Epoxy Specimen Loaded in Tension at a Strain Rate of $0.70 \epsilon/\text{sec}$.

Fig. 7. Load and Strain Records for $[90_8]$ S-Glass/Epoxy Specimen Loaded in Tension at a Strain Rate of $6.3 \epsilon/\text{sec}$.

Fig. 8. Load and Strain Records for [90g] Graphite/Epoxy Specimen Loaded in Tension at a Strain Rate of $0.80 \epsilon/\text{sec}$.

Fig. 9. Load and Strain Records for [90g] Graphite/Epoxy Specimen Loaded in Tension at a Strain Rate of $10 \epsilon/\text{sec}$.

Table II

TRANSVERSE PROPERTIES OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES AT VARIOUS STRAIN RATES

Material	Average Strain Rate (ϵ/sec)	Maximum Strain Rate (ϵ/sec)	Time to Failure (ms)	Modulus E_{22} GPa (10^6 psi)	Poisson's Ratio ν_{21}	Strength S_{22T} MPa (ksi)	Ult. Strain ϵ_{22}^u ($10^{-3}\epsilon$)
Boron/Epoxy	1.4×10^{-4}	1.4×10^{-4}	20×10^3	22.0 (3.1)	0.02	56 (8.1)	2.9
	2.8×10^{-4}	2.8×10^{-4}	10×10^3	19.0 (2.8)	0.014	56 (8.1)	2.9
	0.23	0.25	14.0	19.0 (2.8)	0.001	47 (6.8)	2.7
	0.55	0.60	8.6	15.2 (2.2)	0.007	55 (8.0)	3.3
	0.60	0.70	8.8	14.7 (2.1)	0.007	59 (8.5)	3.7
	4.5	5.8	0.65	-	0.012	-	3.0
	14	19	0.35	15.9 (2.3)	0.011	78 (11.3)	4.5
	20	27	0.35	13.4 (1.9)	0.013	76 (11.0)	5.7
	Graphite/Epoxy	2.8×10^{-4}	2.8×10^{-4}	13×10^3	8.3 (1.2)	0.005	30 (4.4)
2.8×10^{-4}		2.8×10^{-4}	10×10^3	7.8 (1.1)	0.007	23 (3.3)	2.9
0.35		0.75	7.5	7.1 (1.0)	0.009	25 (3.6)	3.1
0.35		0.80	7.4	6.9 (1.03)	0.011	30 (4.4)	3.7
8.2		10.0	0.50	9.3 (1.35)	0.005	32 (4.7)	3.6
8.7		10.3	0.55	9.1 (1.32)	0.004	32 (4.7)	3.4
S-Glass/Epoxy	1.4×10^{-4}	1.4×10^{-4}	33×10^3	19 (2.8)	0.10	79 (11.4)	4.6
	2.8×10^{-4}	2.8×10^{-4}	12×10^3	21 (3.1)	0.10	61 (8.8)	3.3
	0.40	0.50	9.7	20.6 (3.0)	0.08	81 (11.7)	4.0
	0.40	0.60	10	20.2 (2.9)	0.09	78 (11.3)	4.0
	6.3	6.3	0.90	17.1 (2.5)	0.07	75 (11.0)	4.9
	6.8	6.8	0.70	-	0.09	-	3.1
	13	13	0.70	-	0.09	-	4.5
	11	18	0.55	16.2 (2.3)	0.06	82 (12.0)	5.3

Fig. 10. Load and Strain Records for $[10_6]$ Boron/Epoxy Off-Axis Specimen Loaded in Tension at a Strain Rate of $0.57 \epsilon/\text{sec}$.

2 $\mu\text{s}/\text{div}$

Fig. 11. Load and Strain Records for $[10_6]$ Graphite/Epoxy Off-Axis Specimen Loaded in Tension at a Strain Rate of $0.41 \epsilon/\text{sec}$.

500 $\mu\text{s}/\text{div}$

Fig. 12. Load and Strain Records for $[10_6]$ Graphite/Epoxy Off-Axis Specimen Loaded in Tension at a Strain Rate of $4 \epsilon/\text{sec}$.

Table III

INTRALAMINAR SHEAR PROPERTIES OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES AT HIGH STRAIN RATE

Material	Average Strain Rate (ϵ/sec)	Initial Strain Rate (ϵ/sec)	Time to Failure (ms)	Shear Modulus G_{12} GPa (10^6 psi)	Shear Strength S_{12} MPa (ksi)	Ultimate Shear Strain ϵ_{12-3} ($10^{-3}\epsilon$)
Boron/Epoxy	1.4×10^{-4}	1.4×10^{-4}	33×10^3	5.4 (0.80)	62.3 (9.1)	7.26
	2.8×10^{-4}	2.8×10^{-4}	17×10^3	6.2 (0.90)	56.9 (8.2)	7.60
	-	-	6.5	-	56.5 (8.2)	-
	0.59	0.48	6.6	6.8 (0.99)	65.9 (9.6)	5.43
	0.57	0.47	6.5	7.0 (1.02)	66.1 (9.6)	6.71
	2.8	4.1	1.5	7.9 (1.14)	76.7(11.1)	6.99
	2.6	5.7	1.0	7.2 (1.04)	62.5 (9.1)	5.46
	2.7	6.3	1.4	8.1 (1.18)	76.3(11.1)	5.42
	3.3	6.8	1.2	6.7 (0.97)	72.9(10.6)	7.21
	3.9	7.7	0.8	7.7 (1.12)	-	-
	Graphite/ Epoxy	2.8×10^{-4}	2.8×10^{-4}	13×10^3	5.8 (0.84)	53.7 (7.8)
2.8×10^{-4}		2.8×10^{-4}	7.5×10^3	6.1 (0.89)	34.8 (5.1)	3.10
0.15		0.28	9.0	6.2 (0.90)	-	-
-		-	6.7	-	62.8 (9.1)	-
0.41		0.41	6.8	7.5 (1.08)	56.4 (8.2)	3.10
0.52		0.50	6.0	7.7 (1.11)	59.1 (8.6)	5.45
2.4		4.0	1.2	7.6 (1.10)	68.2 (9.9)	4.27
2.3		5.4	1.1	7.2 (1.05)	65.0 (9.4)	3.46
S-Glass/ Epoxy	2.8×10^{-4}	2.8×10^{-4}	17×10^3	4.5 (0.65)	59.0 (8.6)	7.0
	0.34	0.29	15.6	4.3 (0.62)	-	-
	-	-	4.8	-	73.1 (10.6)	-
	2.8	2.8	4.2	-	67.8 (9.8)	-
	12.6	20	2.1	4.3 (0.62)	56.6 (8.2)	13.0
Kevlar 49/ Epoxy	2.8×10^{-4}	2.8×10^{-4}	12×10^3	1.84(0.27)	16.4 (2.37)	4.65
	0.29	0.23	9.2	1.97(0.29)	12.2 (1.77)	4.25
	0.30	0.29	10.0	2.03(0.29)	15.3 (2.22)	4.99
	0.44	0.44	7.6	1.90(0.28)	13.2 (1.91)	5.40
	14	12.9	0.75	1.52(0.22)	16.8 (2.44)	14.74

increase in strength and ultimate strain with strain rate was noticed. In the case of in-plane shear properties, the boron/epoxy and graphite/epoxy showed definite trends of increasing shear modulus and shear strength with strain rate. Strength values approximately fifteen percent higher than static were measured at strain rates of the order of 5-10m/m/sec.

Acknowledgement

The work reported here was sponsored by the NASA-Lewis Research Center, Cleveland, Ohio. We are grateful to Dr. C.C. Chamis of NASA-Lewis for his encouragement and cooperation and to Messrs. R. LaBedz, T. Niirio, and M. Senninger of IITRI for their assistance.

References

1. Daniel, I.M. and Liber, T.: "Wave Propagation in Fiber Composite Laminates," IITRI Report D6073-III, for NASA-Lewis Research Center; NASA CR-135086, June 1976.
2. Zimmer, J.E. and Cost, James R.: "Determination of the Elastic Constants of a Unidirectional Fiber Composite Using Ultrasonic Velocity Measurements," J. Acoust. Soc. of America, Vol. 47, No. 3, 1970, pp. 795-803.
3. Gieske, J.H. and Allred, R.E.: "Elastic Constants of B-Al Composites by Ultrasonic Velocity Measurements," Exper. Mechanics, Vol. 14, No. 4, Apr. 1974, pp. 158-165.
4. Gibson, R.F. and Plunkett, R.: "Dynamic Mechanical Behavior of Fiber-Reinforced Composites: Measurements and Analysis," J. Composite Materials, Vol. 10, Oct. 1976, pp. 325-341.
5. Rotem, A., and Lifshitz, J.: "Longitudinal Strength of Unidirectional Fibrous Composite Under High Rate of Loading," Proc. of 26th Annual Tech. Conf. 1971, Reinforced Plastics/Composites Division, The Soc. of Plastics Industry, Sect. 10-G, Feb. 1971.
6. Lifshitz, J.: "Impact Strength of Angle Ply Fiber Reinforced Materials," J. Composite Materials, Vol. 10, Jan. 1976, pp. 92-101.
7. Armenakas, A.E. and Sciammarella, C.A.: "Response of Glass-fiber-reinforced Epoxy Specimens to High Rates of Tensile Loading," Exper. Mechanics, Vol. 13, Oct. 1973, pp. 433-440.
8. Sierakowski, R.L., Nevill, G.E., Ross, C.A., and Jones, E.R.: "Dynamic Compressive Strength and Failure of Steel Reinforced Epoxy Composites," J. Composite Materials, Vol. 5, July 1971, pp. 362-377.
9. Daniel, I.M. and Liber, T.: "Strain Rate Effects on Mechanical Properties of Fiber Composites," IITRI Report D6073-IV, for NASA-Lewis Research Center; NASA CR-135087, June 1976.
10. Daniel, I.M. and Liber, T.: "Lamination Residual Stresses in Fiber Composites," IITRI Report D6073-I, for NASA-Lewis Research Center; NASA CR-134826, March 1975.
11. Daniel, I.M. and Liber, T.: "Lamination Residual Stresses in Hybrid Composites," IITRI Report D6073-II, for NASA-Lewis Research Center; NASA CR-135085, June 1976.